

Widening Activities 2019

Mentorship Programme

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CESSDA Widening Workshop 2019

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 cessda.eu

 @CESSDA_Data

Context of the mentorship

Helpdesk

Main goal

To provide an online information and email service where partners can get advice and feedback regarding the development of their DAS and their plans for joining CESSDA.

Mentorship programme

Main goal

To offer one-on-one support during 2019 matching project SPs with interested partners and assisting them in defining and realizing their short-term goals.

◆ Resources

All project partners involved – 4.75 PMs in total
FORS (lead, 1.5), CSDA (1), SND (1), ADP (0.75), TARKI (0.5)

◆ One deliverable

12.2019 - Report from operation of the helpdesk and the mentorship programme

Three main activities

1. Select partners for the mentorship, assign a mentor and set the rules

Dec. 2018: Information on the mentorship and how to apply sent to partners

Jan. 2019 – kick off meeting:

- Review of the applications received, selection of partners and allocation of mentors
- Discussion on broad rules for the mentorship

2. Active mentoring

Feb.-Nov. 2019: Running mentorships

3. Report on each mentorship

Dec. 2019: Written by both the mentee and the mentor

	Dec.	Jan.	Feb.	Mar.	April	May	June	July	Aug.	Sept.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.
1. Selection	■	■											
2. Mentoring			■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	
3. Report													■

Applications

Interested partners were asked to submit their proposals for the mentorship programme in a short document answering the following questions:

- Where are you in the process of building the archive? What have you achieved/developed lately?
- What are your goals for 2019?
- Based on these goals, where can the CESSDA Widening group actively help you? What are the expected benefits from our help?

Partners' goals & interests

	CREDI (BiH)	FFZG (Croatia)	Unidata (Italy)	CPC (Kosovo)	LiDA (Lithuania)	MK DASS (Macedonia)	DCS (Serbia)
Organisation models (node)		Establishment plan	Network & NDP				
Policies, legal procedures							
Data curation, preservation, dissemination			Workflow & materials for researchers			Quali data, formats, R	Workflow, OAI
Dataverse (implem. and workflow)							
Staff		Job descriptions		Capacity building			
Advocacy	Advocacy plan for policy		Research funding agenda	Diverses stakeholders	Ministry		
Networks		Technical infrastructure	Data producers				
CESSDA membership		Membership			Application		
Other					Guidance on CTS	Risk assessment plan	

Rules

- Regular interactions are expected between the mentor and the mentee.
- Discussion on the mentorship activities to realise the goals.

The mentor:

- is the reference contact person of the mentee
- is responsible for actively accompanying the mentee
- documents the interactions
- stays in contact with the other mentors to find solutions together if necessary

The mentee partner:

- agrees to collaborate with the mentor
- provides a final report on the mentorship
 - reports on the goals and activities realised during the year
 - discusses what went well and what could be improved for future mentoring activities
 - give an update of the situation and plans for 2020.

Activities I

CREDI (BiH) & TARKI

Visit to TARKI: discussion on issues to create a stable infrastructure (e.g. institutionalisation, data catalogue, network). Feedback on preservation policy and other documents. Collaboration on INTERREG proposal.

FFZG (Croatia) & ADP

Visit to ADP: assistance with employment categories and copyright issues, feedback on the establishment/action plan. FTF meeting in Copenhagen and Skopje.

LiDA (Lithuania) & ADP

Visit to ADP: guidance on CoreTrustSeal requirements, support on preservation policy, acquainted with various aspects of the work in the ADP. FTF meeting in Copenhagen.

Activities II

CPC (Kosovo) & CSDA

Visit to CSDA: presentations & discussion on CSDA data services, policy dialogue and advocacy, CESSDA resources, tools and services to further develop the DAS. Transfer of Kosovan RRPP data. Two virtual meetings and FTF meeting in Skopje.

Unidata (Italy) & SND

Changes in the proposal. Feedbacks on UniData's internal manual. Two virtual meetings.

MK DASS (Macedonia) & SND

Discussion about staffing - how to train new staff, licenses and other agreements. SND sent documents and links. Two virtual meetings. FTF meeting in Skopje.

DCS (Serbia) & FORS

Changes in the proposal: transfer of Serbian RRPP data from FORS to DCS. Contracts signed. Transfer ready. Virtual tour of data archiving with FORSbase (planned). One virtual meeting.

Reflection on the mentorship

Successes

- **Progress in / achievement of some goals**
- **Site visits**
Fruitful discussions
- **Positive collaboration**
Successful collaboration
Base for future collaboration

Difficulties

- **Context specific**
Delay in (funding) decisions
→ change in the mentorship proposal
→ stop of activities
- **Contact**
Uncertainty on who will take the initiative to contact
Staying in regular contact
- **Goals**
Specific issues (e.g. budget) on which we can not help
- **Timing of the mentorship**
More helpful after institutionalisation

Thank you for your attention!

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